

PRINCIPLES OF INCREASING SPEECH COMPETENCE WHEN STUDYING FOREIGN LANGUAGES OF SPECIALISTS IN HIGHER MILITARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS (USING THE EXAMPLE OF FRENCH)

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Abstract. *This article deals with the problems of developing communicative skills competence in foreign language learning by the specialists of higher military educational establishments.*

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Showing the basics of improving a specialist's speech competence when studying foreign languages in higher military educational institutions has become one of the pressing tasks of the age of information technology. The reason is that in modern conditions, knowledge of foreign languages is one of the main factors influencing the readiness of a graduate of military educational institutions to remain competitive and take a worthy place not only in their social and professional environment. Today, the solution of these problems is facilitated by psychological and pedagogical approaches to teaching foreign languages in higher military educational institutions.

In the context of political and economic reforms in Uzbekistan, new demands are placed on the system of higher military education. In this regard, intensive research is being conducted on the problems of creating a psychological and pedagogical comfortable training environment for military specialists, the selection of sufficient information, technical and communication tools and teaching methods, and the scientific organization of creative pedagogical activities.

Despite the great interest in the problem of using a technological approach to the language training of future officers, the theoretical and practical aspects of the formation of language competence of cadets of higher military educational institutions have been little studied.

For example, the presence of nasal sounds in French, a combination of two or more letters forming one sound, cause certain difficulties in learning this language: en, un, on, in, im, em, oin; oh, oh, oh, hey. Therefore, it is necessary to train military specialists to recognize and reproduce sounds that are different or absent in the French language.

The introduction of a student-centered approach to teaching a foreign language largely depends on how the teacher perceives students and what personal qualities he considers the most important. Particularly important to a learner-centered approach are qualities that reflect each learner's self-awareness.

At the same time, literacy today consists of identifying and developing the potential learning abilities of a future specialist, maintaining and strengthening educational motivation, and forming important and significant knowledge for the individual, that is, a military specialist, in the learning process. .

For example, when using military terms, you need to pay attention to the following aspects.

Le soldat doit <i>charger</i> le fusil. Le troupe <i>est chargé</i> d'une mission principale.	A soldier must <i>load</i> his weapon. The main task is <i>assigned</i> to the army.
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In the first sentence the verb load is used to read, and in the second sentence it is used to *assigned*.

The phrase "l'armée de mer" was used as a synonym for "la Marine de guerre", but military experts should note that in later years the two terms were adopted as the phrase "Marine Nationale".

Social and psychological optimization of the educational process, the creation of a psychologically and pedagogically acceptable learning environment, the creation of an “engaged learning” environment, the introduction of professionally oriented learning technology based on the organization of independent work of cadets, require finding ways to increase the effectiveness of the professional training of future military specialists. The technology of teaching a foreign language is considered as an optimization activity with all its features.

Undoubtedly, one of the foundations for improving the speech competence of a specialized specialist when studying a foreign language in higher military educational institutions is the development of listening comprehension. However, when learning French, students have difficulty listening and practice less. Azhar Ilyas Boutte, a researcher at the University of Grenoble, believes that the use of ICT in teaching French, developing oral language through listening comprehension and real-time live listening is essential for language learning. In this process, the student uses various sources to find the meaning of the oral message, the detail of the context and general knowledge about the world increases.¹

Based on the structure of the language competence of the future military specialist, the object of testing and evaluation may be a component of his knowledge - the language awareness of cadets (vocabulary, grammar and actual use of the language), the maturity of types of speech activity (speaking, reading, listening), writing), as well as the use of language in extracurricular activities (additional reading based on interests, searching for information on the Internet, preparing abstract translations of real scientific and popular science sources), practical conferences and helping teachers in creating didactic materials and trainings. manuals, etc.).

In the practice of higher military education, the level of development of the language competence of cadets and students is, as a rule, assessed subjectively. Assessing oral communication skills has traditionally focused on pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammatical errors. We can see this in the following examples.

In the first sentence, *sortir* is expressed as a transitive verb meaning to go out, to leave, in

1. Il est <i>sorti</i> de la chambre. 2. Il a <i>sorti</i> de sa poche un petit livre.	He <i>left</i> the room. He <i>took out</i> a small book from his pocket.
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the past tense using the auxiliary verb être, and in the second sentence using the auxiliary verb avoir. Usually our listeners and learners forget that verbs marked with the auxiliary verb être agree with the stem and the possessive case.

According to the early ideas of the scientist N. Chomsky, language works not only in the form of “standard” repeated and produced sentences, but also allows for countless individual creative speech acts.¹

Factors influencing the professional growth of a military specialist can be divided into three main groups:

- individual characteristics (propensity for military service, the presence of qualities necessary for the chosen specialty);
- society's need for these specialists (demand for specialists in a certain profession and a certain level of qualifications, proficiency in computer technology, proficiency in foreign languages);
- nearby opportunities (possibility of protection, a certain level of knowledge, financial situation), etc.

Of course, cadets and students want to quickly develop oral speech. They are given a lot of advice throughout the year, but there is nothing better than following the advice of real professionals. Sometimes language learners are afraid to use words. However, it is important to practice the language regularly and overcome this fear. Grammar and pronunciation problems, as well as vocabulary deficits, will disappear with practice.

In conclusion, it should be noted that improving the speech competence of future officers in higher military educational institutions presupposes the achievement of educational goals. Achieving educational goals is carried out within the framework of the humanization of military education, this means expanding the worldview of cadets and cadets, increasing their general culture and level of education, as well as the culture of thinking, communication and speech. The speech competence of the student and listener is definitely formed by listening to the French language for half an hour to an hour every day. Therefore, cadets and our students must participate in discussions in various situations and achieve the level of ability to express their thoughts in a foreign language.

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